

STUDIES IN HYDROGEN BOND FORMATION. PART I. AMIDES.

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The Raman spectra of formamide, acetamide and urea were studied in solutions of water and at increased temperatures. From the changes observed in the C=O frequencies, it is concluded that the amides, particularly formamide and acetamide, are highly polymerised at the laboratory temperatures, and that they break up into lower polymers at higher temperatures as well as in solutions in polar solvents like water.

Latimer and Rodebush (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **42**, 1419) proposed that association between molecules takes place through a hydrogen or a proton bond, the conditions for the formation of which are (i) a lone pair of electrons on an atom to act as donor ; (ii) hydrogen on molecule from which it is easily removed as hydrogen ion.

Evidence of association has generally been obtained from measurements of heats of mixing, of viscosity, of dielectric constant and of freezing points. But with the developments of new physical methods of studying the structure of molecules, the problem of association has been studied by X-ray diffraction, electron diffraction, infra-red absorption and Raman effect.

The study of the nature of solution by the application of Raman effect has been the subject of a series of investigations by Ramakrishna Rao and collaborators (*Proc. K. Akad. wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1930, **33**, 638 ; *Indian J. Phys.*, 1937, **11**, 143). Rao (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, **A 130**, 489 ; 1934, **A148**, 489) was the first to use this method for the elucidation of the constitution of water and on the basis of the observed changes in the structure of the Raman band for water with temperature, he postulated the existence of different types of polymers of H₂O molecule. This has been extended by Rao and Koteswaram (*Indian J. Phys.* 1938, **12**, 63) to the study of association in heavy water and by Koteswaram (*Z. Physik*, 1938, **110**, 118 ; 1939, **112**, 395) to the lower members of the fatty acids.

In the course of a general investigation on molecular association, the author has studied some of the amides and the present paper reports the results of work on formamide, acetamide and urea.

The high boiling points and dielectric constants of the amides have long been recognised as evidence for a high degree of association. Kumler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 600) has pointed out that this evidence as well as that of cryoscopic data point to a marked difference

in the behaviour of the amides when the hydrogens attached to the nitrogen are replaced by alkyl groups. This evidence points to hydrogen bonding as the mechanism by which association takes place. Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2, 3257) and Sugden (*ibid.*, 1924, 128, 1177) measured the parachor values of certain amides at different temperatures and found that they increased steadily with rise of temperature. A drift of this nature was explained as due to the presence of associated molecules at the lower temperature. Copley, Zellhoefer and Marvel (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2666) from the extremely low solubility of monofluorodichloromethane in formamide and acetamide, have suggested the formation of large polymers. Busweil and Rodebush (*ibid.*, 1938, 60, 2444) from the infra-red study of the amides come to the conclusion that amides show a strong tendency towards association. More recently, Saxena (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1940, 11A, 53) studied the association in formamide by the use of Raman effect.

With a view to studying the association characteristics of the amides, the author has studied the effect of temperature and of dilution with water.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangement for exciting the Raman spectra was essentially the same as that proposed by Wood, (*Phil. Mag.*, 1928, 6, 729). The light from the Hg-arc was condensed by a 9" glass condenser on to the Wood's tube containing the solution to be investigated. A combination of two filters consisting of a solution of sodium nitrite and a solution of the proper strength of iodine in carbon tetrachloride was chosen and placed between the condenser and the scattering medium. This served to eliminate the 4047 line of the arc and beyond on the shorter wave-length region, and also the continuous spectrum between 4358 Å and 4916 Å, present in the light from the mercury arc. Care was taken to run the arc at a low voltage, which helps to reduce the continuum considerably. Thus the exciting source is the 4358 line of the mercury arc which is undoubtedly the best mercury line and the Raman lines appear between 4358 and 4916 Å, a region free of mercury lines.

The scattered light was focussed on the slit of the spectrograph by means of an achromatic lens. A two-prism spectrograph of high light-gathering power was used to record the Raman spectrum on Ilford Isochrome plates. A comparison spectrum of copper was given on the same plate using a Hartmann's diaphragm and the wave-length measured

on a Hilger comparator. For such of the lines, which are broad and diffuse, the location of the maximum with the comparator not being possible, a microphotometric record of the entire Raman spectrum was taken. From this record it was easy to find both the position of such lines and their quality in respect of width and diffuseness.

For work at higher temperatures, the Wood's tube, containing the substance to be investigated, was placed inside a cylindrical electrical heater of 5 cm. in diameter and 28 cm. long, open at either end. The heater was provided on one side with a window of 2×14 cm. for allowing the incident radiation. By this arrangement the temperature could be kept within a range of $\pm 0.5^\circ$.

Purification of Solutions.

All the amides investigated show a very strong continuous background masking to a great extent the Raman lines. Merck's bidistilled formamide, when kept for exposure showed a strong continuous spectrum in the region $4046\text{\AA}$ — $4916\text{\AA}$ and beyond to the green line of the mercury arc. So, the liquid was further purified by distilling it twice at low pressure and at 110° . The sample thus obtained was found to be free to a large extent from the continuum and was used throughout the course of these investigations.

In the case of solutions of acetamide and urea, the method previously adopted by the author for purification of sugar (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1940, **14**, 207) was found to be successful. It consists in shaking the solution with Norit A (the carbon used being about 3% of the weight of the amide in the solution) and then heated for 15 to 20 minutes at 70° with stirring. The solution was then filtered through a sintered glass funnel in which a filter paper of fine pore was put. The filtrate was collected and poured on to the filter repeatedly 5 or 6 times, thus removing the dust particles from the filter system. The filtrate was then allowed to flow directly into the Wood's tube. The solutions thus prepared were remarkably clear and gave spectra entirely free from continuum. Control experiments with Norit A in distilled water were done in order to make sure that there were no Raman lines or bands not found in pure water. The remarkable property of the decolorising carbon on the removal of continuum could be explained on the well known property of carbons to adsorb impurities, and it might be that the fluorescent impurities, which are responsible for the continuous spectrum, were removed during the above method of purification. Double distilled conductivity water was always used in the study of the amides at different dilutions.

Formamide.

The Raman spectrum of this substance has been previously studied by Kohlrausch and Pongratz (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1934, **B27**, 176,) and more recently by Saxena (*loc. cit.*). This could be obtained in 15 hours by the author. The effect of water on formamide was studied at 75%, 50% and 25% concentration of formamide, and proportionately increased exposures were given for the different dilutions. The effect of solution in some of the non-polar solvents like benzene, ether, etc. could not be

FIG. 1.
Formamide.

studied owing to the general insolubility of all the amides investigated in these solvents. Formamide was investigated at 30° and at 140°. Figs. 1 (A and B) contains the microphotometric curves of the Raman spectra

of formamide taken under different conditions. Table I gives the Raman frequencies of this substance. The figures in parenthesis indicate the relative visual estimates of the intensities. For the sake of brevity, the assignment of the various frequencies are given in column IV of the table. In columns I and II are given the results of the previous investigators for purposes of comparison.

TABLE I.

Formamide.

Kohlrausch and Pongratz (1934)	Saxena (1940)	Author.	Assignment.
	200 (3) br	201 (3) V. br	
608 (4)	603 (4)	600 (4)	
	700 (o)		
	780 (o)		
1005 (4)			
1050 (1)	1048 (o)	1051 (1)	C-N
1094 (2) br	1095 (2) br	1094 (3) br	
1314 (6)	1305 (5) V. br	1309 (5) br	
		1341 (1, s)	
1390 (10) s	1391 (10) s	1390 (10) s	
1599 (1)	1591 (1)	1594 (2)	C=O
1672 ± 11 (2)	1672 (2)	1672 (3)	
	2008 (o)		
	2083 (1)		
	2695 (o)		
	2766 (1)		
2882 (8) br	2885 (8) br	2884 (8)	Valence C-H
	3176 (4)	3183	N-H
	3265 (1)	3215	
	3338 (2)	3298	
3347 (1)	3338 (2)		
3376 (1)	3480		

The intensity and frequency changes of the various Raman lines of formamide under the different conditions studied are discussed in brief below.

(i) $\Delta\nu=600$. With dilution in water it diminishes in intensity and becomes broad and diffuse at 25% dilution. Similar changes are observed with increase of temperature from 30° to 140°

(ii) $\Delta\nu=1051$. This is the faint component accompanying the 1094 line and disappears at higher temperatures.

(iii) $\Delta\nu=1341$. This is a weak line which is not present at the laboratory temperature but appears at the higher temperature. A similar effect was not noticed in dilutions with water, probably due to the increased continuum in solutions.

(iv) $\Delta\nu=1390$. The sharp line at 1390 shows a shift of 6 cm^{-1} at 25% dilution. A similar change was observed with increase of temperature.

(v) $\Delta\nu=1594, 1672$. These are the C=O frequencies. At the higher temperature the intensity of the 1594 line is considerably decreased. The line 1672 is broad with the sharp edge towards the $4358\text{\AA}$ line of the mercury arc, and has an intensity maximum at the edge. At the higher temperature, this maximum shifts to longer wave-length and there is a shift of about 8 cm^{-1} . The effect of dilution has a similar change on the Raman spectrum of this substance in this region.

(vi) $\Delta\nu=2884$. This is the C—H frequency and indicates no change either in solutions or with temperature changes.

Acetamide.

The Raman spectrum of this substance has previously been studied by Kohlarusch and Pongratz (*loc. cit.*) in the molten state and by Anantha-krishnan (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, 5A, 200) in the crystal state. As far as the author is aware, there is no work reported on this substance in solutions of water. The Raman spectrum of this substance was obtained in 10 hours. The microphotometric curves of the Raman spectra taken under different conditions are given in Fig. 2 (A—C). Table II gives the Raman frequencies of acetamide along with those reported by the previous investigators. The assignment of the frequencies to the respective valence bonds are given in column 4 of the table. The intensity and frequency changes of the various Raman lines of acetamide under the different conditions studied are discussed in brief below.

(i) $\Delta\nu=448, 565$. These are the low frequency lines ascribed to the external oscillation in the molecule. The intensity of these lines falls off and they become diffuse as dilution progresses. A similar change is observed with increase of temperature.

(ii) $\Delta\nu=861, 995$. Of these 861 is the C—C frequency. The 861 line diminishes considerably in intensity with dilution and change of temperature and slightly increases in its frequency, the shift being about 4 cm^{-1} . The

Fig 2.
Acetamide.

weak line at 995, which is ascribed to C—N, disappears at higher dilutions and temperature,

(iii) $\Delta\nu=1124$. It falls off in intensity and becomes diffuse at higher temperatures and changes in frequency by 10 cm^{-1} .

(iv) $\Delta\nu=1323, 1384$. 1323 is a sharp line and tends to disappear at higher dilutions. With increase of temperature the effect is more pronounced. 1384 is a broad line with its intensity maximum towards the exciting line. With increase of temperature and in solutions the line shifts to a higher Raman frequency, the shift being 6 cm^{-1} .

(v) $\Delta\nu=1606, 1667$. There are C=O frequencies. With dilutions in water, 1606 line diminishes in intensity and shifts to 1610. The 1667 line remains very nearly unchanged in dilute solutions. But with increase of temperature more marked changes were observed; the lower frequency disappears altogether and merges into a broad band with intensity maximum at 1673.

(vi) $\Delta\nu=2930, 2965$. There are the C-H frequencies. Of these 2930 is the stronger line. They remain unchanged both in solutions in water and at increased temperatures.

TABLE II.

Kohlransch and Pongratz (molten).	Ananthakrishnan. (crystal).	Author. (aq. soln.).	Assignment.
236 (o)			
448 (3)	455 (1) S	448 (3)	
564 (3)		565 (4)	
862 (7) br	875 (8) S	861 (8) S	C—C
		995 (1)	} C—N
1119 (3) br	1147 (9) S	1124 (3) br	
1344 (3) br	1354 (3)	1323 (3) br	
1387 (3) br	1397 (3) diff.	1384 (4) br	
1422 (3)			
1611 (2)	1594 (1) diff.	1606 (2) br	} C=O
1660 $\pm$ 9 (3) br		1667 (2) br	
2933 (6) br	2933 (10) S	2930 (5)	} valence C—H
2958 (2)	2970 (n) d	2965 (1)	
	3020 (n) d		
	3150 (6) br		
	3286 (1) diff.		
	3351 (4) diff.		

Urea.

The Raman spectrum of this substance has previously been studied by Kohlrausch and Pongratz (*loc. cit.*) and Edsall (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1935 4, 1) in aqueous solution, and Ananthakrishnan (*loc. cit.*) in the crystal state. The Raman spectrum of this substance could be obtained in 20 hours. The microphotometric curves of the spectra taken under different conditions are given in Fig. 3 (A and B). No marked changes either in intensity

Fig 3.

Urea.

or frequency were observed with urea in solutions with water.

(i) $\Delta\nu=520, 584$. Except for decrease in intensity, the lines remain unchanged.

(ii) $\Delta\nu=1175$. It becomes sharper with dilution and finally tends to disappear.

(iii) $\Delta\nu=1593, 1663, 1726$. These are the C=O frequencies. Of these the 1593 only disappears at higher dilutions. The other two lines 1663, and 1726 remained unchanged in their frequency and in their outward appearance.

Table III gives the frequencies of urea along with those reported by other observers.

TABLE III.

Edsall (aq. solution.).	Ananthakrishnan (crystal).	Author (aq. solution).	
521 (1)		520 (2)	
584 (1)		584 (1)	
1000 (6)	1012 (10) S	1000 (10) S	} C-N
1170 (1) V. br	1171 (3) diff.	1175 (2) br	
1468 (0)	1465		
1580 (0)	1537 (2)	1593 (1)	} C=O
1666 (1) b	1576 (3)	1663 (2) br	
1768 (1)		1726 (1) br	
3230 (1)	3243 (2) diff.		
	3334 (4) diff.		
3380 (3) br	3353 (5) diff.		
3489 (1) br	3434 (5)		

DISCUSSION.

The classical structure assigned to the unsubstituted amides is

But certain reactions of the amides, such as alkylation, indicate that they may have the alternative tautomeric structures as

Kohrausch and Pongratz (*loc. cit.*) ascribe the two frequencies in acetamide, $\Delta\nu=1611, 1660$ observed in the C=O region as due to the tautomeric modifications as suggested above. Krishnamurty (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1931, 6, 309) suggests a similar tautomeric arrangement in the case of urea as:

and Pauling ("Nature of Chemical Bond", 1939) has suggested

But as is shown later in the discussion, it is not possible to have a great proportion of the tautomer molecules. This is supported by the dipole moment measurements of Kumler and Porter (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 2549).

From the changes observed with dilution and temperature, it can be said that the acid amides, formamide and acetamide, show a greater tendency towards association. It is not possible to deduce with certainty whether the intramolecular association is the result of $\text{NH} \leftarrow \text{N}$ or $\text{NH} \leftarrow \text{O}$ bonding, and as the $\text{O} \rightarrow \text{H}$ bonding is much stronger than the $\text{N} \rightarrow \text{H}$ bonding, it could be expected that the former type of bonding would exist in associated amides. The work of Rodebush and Buswell (*loc.cit.* also *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 3252) on glycylglycine ethyl ester, and some of the monosubstituted amides show definitely a strong infra-red absorption a little beyond 3μ indicating bonded $\text{O}-\text{H}$ rather than $\text{N}-\text{H}$. So, the associated molecule in an amide could be represented as

In such a postulated molecule, the hydrogens occur not involved in bond formation, attached directly to the ring of the double molecule, and these additional hydrogens might interfere with the formation of stable dimers. We have an analogy in the case of formic acid, where in the pure acid, the dimers give way to polymers, because of the bonding action of the hydrogen attached to the carbon. Thus, in the case of unsubstituted amides, it can be said that the association proceeds to a higher stage and forms large sized polymers as

or by the "fusing" of dimers as

But the formation of a polymer as represented in the second type requires sharing of the second pair of electrons on the oxygens. So, it could be said that the amides exist as linear polymers as shown in type I.

Of course, in the case of monosubstituted amides, the hydrogen is replaced by R and the existence of dimers in these amides has been shown by Rodebush and Buswell (*loc. cit.*) and they also suggest that enolisation can take place only in associated molecules.

In the case of solutions of formamide and acetamide in water, we have an associated solute in solution in another associated solvent, and it is well known that in such a system there will be the tendency for mutual dissociation. Thus, any change caused by association or dissociation of the molecules must affect the frequencies of the C=O group most, as they are nearest to the hydrogen bond.

The CH₃ and C—C linkages are not affected to such a large extent. With the formation of a hydrogen bond, the C=O binding weakens, thus giving rise to a diminished frequency. While, with the breaking up of such a bond the opposite effect takes place, resulting in a strengthening of the binding and a consequent increase in frequency.

The changes observed in formamide and acetamide, definitely indicate that there is dissociation of the more complex molecules into simpler ones as is evidenced in formamide by the shift of the C=O frequency 1672 to 1680 cm.⁻¹ The 1594 line almost disappears at the higher temperature, and at 25% dilution. So, the lower frequency seems to be characteristic of the associated molecules. Similar changes in the carbonyl frequency were also noticed in acetamide. Koteswaram (*loc. cit.*) observed analogous changes in the carbonyl frequency of the carboxyl group in formic and acetic acids. The 600 line in formamide, and the 565 line in acetamide,

could be ascribed to an external oscillation in the molecule. The increased diffuseness of this line with dilution or with increase of temperature indicates that there may be the superposition of two lines—one corresponding to the associated molecules at the lower temperature, and the other due to the depolymerised molecules in solution or at higher temperatures. Similar changes were also observed in the author's work on glycerine (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1940, 4, 365).

The feeble component lines 1051 in formamide and 995 in acetamide may be due to the C-N oscillations of the associated molecules and therefore naturally disappear at the higher temperatures and dilutions as the molecules giving rise to these lines are depolymerised. Thus, it would be seen from the foregoing results that the molecular complexity of the amides decreases with increase of temperature or with dilution. Similar conclusions were arrived at by Turner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 2069) by the measurement of association factors at different temperatures, and by Smith (*loc. cit.*) from measurements of the parachor value between 18° and 50°.

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